

Frame analysis in analyzing Ukrainian female media images

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Annotation. This research takes a gender-based problem Ukrainian magazines as research object, analyzing the characteristics of its reports on Ukrainian social gender issues and Ukrainian female media images, and analyzing the audiences' views to feminism and Ukrainian women, analyzing the role of media in promoting the development of feminism and the changes in Ukrainian women's social status. To investigate the constructed text and the impact it has on sociocultural and ideological events, frame analysis was applied, being combined with other methods such as text analysis, discourse analysis, and semiotic analysis. It was determined that framing allows to choose certain aspects of reality and make them more visible in the communicative process, leading to a particular interpretation. The conclusion was made that feminist discourse is inherent in publications on various topics: politics, culture, and science, whereas the frame of "feminism" is associated with few publications; most publications are associated with the frame of "gender".

Keywords: feminism, female, gender, frame analysis, reports, media image.

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, feminism has gained spectacular levels of visibility and notability in the media, especially online. In fact, Lind & Salo (2002) believe that with the rapid development of the media, the improvement of women's social status and the development of the media present a complementary and positive correlation. Feminist movement in Ukraine is closely related with the political turmoil of the country and is constrained by the strong patriarchal order deeply rooted in its history and politics. Ukraine has witnessed the evolution of its feminist movements and the links between feminist agenda with national discourse.

In modern Ukrainian society, the phenomenon of feminism is characterized as a certain organization of social activities of men and women, which is directed against discrimination against women, for equity and equality of men and women in all of the social spheres, for emancipation and humanization of society. However, it is important to note that on the practical side the content of this term is much broader and more diverse. Its transformation is realized in the process of economic, social and political development, transformations in the world on the basis of democratic principles, changing the system of values and public consciousness.

The purpose of the article is to address the media image of Ukrainian feminism by means of the content analysis and discourse analysis of Ukrainian gender-focused magazines (2003-2018). The study considers that, according to Lind & Salo (2002), by building the media image of Ukrainian feminism movement and the media image of Ukrainian women, the media can influence, including promote or curb the development of Ukrainian feminism as well as the status of Ukrainian women. However, there has been little research on the presentation of media reports on the feminist movement especially in the context of political and national discourse. At the same time, it is also difficult to find relevant research on

people's perception of feminist media content that in turn tends to shape readers or viewers understanding of this topic.

The methodology of the study draws on the theory of feminism and is aimed at conducting content analysis and discourse analysis of Ukrainian gender-oriented magazines (2003-2018) discussing gender issues in Ukraine, as well as addressing feminist ideas.

RESULTS

It can be hypothesised that gender-oriented magazines conduct gender-related reports, and the content of the report is based on a certain frame. This frame is the views and interests of the magazine editorial board, and can also be said to be based on the views and interests of various organizations. This frame of the reports is not invariant, it has been changing with Ukraine's independence, the feminist movements and the awakening of women's awareness of self-protection in Ukrainian society. Therefore, this research believes that in the gender-related and women-related reports, such as those focusing on feminist movement and changes in women's status, as well as the presentation of female media roles, have certain characteristics and certain changes, reflecting the development of feminism and female social status in Ukraine.

The frame theory originally originated in sociology and psychology. It was introduced in the field of communication journalism in the 1980s (Rawlins, 1987). M. Minsky defines *frames* as information data formed in a certain way, reproducing the knowledge gained through experience about a certain stereotypical situation (the concept of "situation" has a general meaning, as it can denote action, image, story, etc.). According to the scientist, graphically, the frame can be represented by a multilevel network consisting of nodes and connections (Minsky, 1979).

Kolyadenko (2013) tried to generalize the variety of interpretations and identified different understandings of the term frame in linguistics:

- 1) frame as a system of choice of language — grammatical rules, lexical units, language categories — related to the prototype scene (Ch. Fillmore);
- 2) frame — a set of standardized actual and potential knowledge about phenomena that have a complex multi-component structure, a holistic view of the multilevel concept (Z. Popova, J. Sternin, A. Babushkin);
- 3) frame — a cognitive model that represents knowledge and assessments related to specific, often recurring situations (F. Ungerer, H.-J. Schmidt);
- 4) frame as a unit of knowledge organized around a concept that contains information about the essential, typical and possible for this concept within a particular culture (T. van Dyck, R. Brand, W. Dressler) (Kolyadenko, 2013, p. 139-144).

Another scholar, V. Rizun, puts forward the definition: "frames are cognitive structures that control our perception and perceptions of the world. The media play an important role in creating mental frameworks that determine the nature and direction of the audience's understanding of reality" (Rizun, 2008, p. 215). That is, a frame is a point of view through which information is presented. It is also a way of compactly storing information in the human mind. Journalists can use this framework both intentionally and unconsciously. The interpretation of information by the audience largely depends on the "framework" chosen by the journalist.

Similarly, G. Pocheptsov (2008) understands frames as ready-made interpretive structures that structure the world around us. The journalist says that in the event of a collision between fact and frame, victory remains behind the frame. The same event can be presented in different ways. It depends on the chosen framework (Pocheptsov, 2008, p. 6). The frame is empty from the beginning. It is only a structure of data about the text and

does not contain any specific information (Goncharenko, 1984, 84).

Therefore, in the analysis, it is crucial to pay attention to all plot elements. The frame is greatly influenced by the headline, the ice, the intonations of the presenter and reporters, the synchronies chosen during the editing, the shots selected by the journalist, and so on. The researcher also believes that frames save a journalist's time and help quickly "pack information" about formal events (Skrypnykova, 2014, p. 1235). Indeed, if some events take place regularly, it is easier for journalists to work with ready-made stencils. At the same time, of course, the originality of the texts is spoiled. However, in the conditions of the information society, where humanity does not have time to follow all the events, this has become a normal phenomenon.

Janou (2011) identifies four aspects of framing: work on meaning-making; implementation through the process of selection, categorization and names; implication through story-telling; construction of meanings (meanings of problems, identities, relations, interactions) (Janou, 2011, p. 93). The researcher considers the main mechanisms of framing name and categorization. First, they give meaning to an object, event or action. Thus, differences are established between, for example, victims and perpetrators, friends and enemies, one's own and others', normal and abnormal, old and new, work and leisure, fight and play — all that matters in these particular circumstances. Naming and categorization are also included in the picture of some actors, not considering others; these operations distinguish between actions and words, facts, and thoughts.

Also, D. Janou considers labelling and evaluation to be effective framing mechanisms. Currently, Ukrainian journalism is actively using markers and evaluative vocabulary. For example, "terrorists", "separatists", "criminal authorities", etc. At the same time, generalizations are often made, and word markers are used about those who are

unaffected. Thus, the "junta" marker, which Ukrainian journalists "borrowed" from the Russians, can often be humorously found in the Ukrainian media. However, this is a negative trend when we teach others to look at ourselves through this marker frame. The strength of the frame is that by joining a given flow of information, a person can come up with everything else, imposing on it their moral assessment. Unlike propaganda, framing is not so obvious. Faced with it every day, we do not think about it (Ptukhina, 2017). Framing plays a big role in advertising and PR because it can directly convince consumers of something. How effective a selling campaign will be to "hook" a potential buyer depends on how effective the entire advertising campaign is. A specialist can cut out unnecessary information about the product and leave it important in setting a framework. At the same time, no one is deceived; just unwanted factors are silenced or mentioned at a minimum (Ptukhina, 2017).

Thus, framing allows you to choose certain aspects of reality and make them more visible in the communicative process, leading the consumer of this information to a particular interpretation of the phenomenon. The basis of framing is the statement that a person decides a phenomenon depending on the form in which information about him will be presented.

In our study, we applied frame theory based on processing information at the media and individual levels and its perception by recipients. In addition, we examined how framing affects people's choices.

Media framing is the way information is presented to an audience. Frames affect the audience's perception of the news; this form of established "agenda" tells what to think and how to think about it. Because social issues are often complex and require considerable baggage of information from different points of view, frames provide a concise understanding of the situation, focusing only on those functions that are of

interest to particular stakeholders. Frames are tools of interpretation that all people use to understand the world. They help us with the difficult task of dealing with complex social problems about our social reality, focusing our attention only on some features that we consider essential.

Framing news or media is a necessary condition for transforming uncertain and unrecognizable events into ones that are gaining in importance. Media framing also serves as a work plan for journalists, allowing them to quickly identify and classify information and "package it effectively for the audience." The concept of media framing may involve the author's intentions, but the motives may also be unconscious. The media conveys to the audience the schemes for the perception and interpretation of information. Framing serves to select some aspects of the received reality and as a tool to make them more imaginative in the communicated text to present a specific problem in the topic, causal interpretation, moral evaluation or making definite and intended recommendations for a solution of problems. Thus, the framing of the media and the presentation of events and news in some way systematically affects how the audience perceives and understands those events and news.

With Ukraine's independence, feminist movements, and the awakening of women's awareness of self-defence in Ukrainian society, the structure of the reports is changing. Thus, this study believes that gender-related reports published in this magazine "I", report on women, such as those focusing on the feminist movement and changing women's status, as well as Presentations of the roles of women in the media, have specific features and inevitable changes that reflect the development of feminism and the social status of women in Ukraine.

Frame refers to people's cognitive structure to recognize and interpret the external objective world (Rawlins, 1987). People's induction, structure and interpretation of real-life experience all

rely on a certain frame (Pan & Kosicki, 1993). The frame enables people to locate, perceive, understand, and summarize a lot of specific information. The media frame is the organizational framework for the information processing of media institutions, which is suitable for the research of various types of media information production and dissemination processes (Gitlin, 2003). This concept is applied to the study of selecting and processing news text and figuring out meaning constructed of a certain media. The principle of the media frame comes from the position of the news media, the editorial policy and the interest relationship with news events, and at the same time is restricted by the special laws of news activities (such as the law of news value) (Gitlin, 2003). These principles stipulate the basic attitude and essential judgment of a media on news events.

Thus, frame analysis can be called a comprehensive research method, including analysis of verbal and nonverbal communication, visual range, and natural selection of facts, frames, and news participants (who appear in the frame). Particular attention should be paid to vocabulary, which may include many markers and evaluative vocabulary, which already form a confident attitude to the situation and do not allow to look objectively.

As O. Sitcak (2012, p. 5) points out, the action of news media is impartial objectivity supply of information, as evidenced by the titles of publications and information programs: "Mirror of the Week", "Windows", "Facts", "Window to the World". Metaphors of mirrors and windows are based on the assumption that they reflect or reflect reality and help us see the world as it is. However, not all events of the day or week are covered by news and newspapers, as this is impossible. Thus, the very choice of topics-events for coverage and their placement in a specific sequence is an ideological process that at least reflects the ideology

and preferences of the publication team (Kulik, 2010, p. 110).

In order to reveal the ideological component of news media, in particular how they not only mediate our perception of reality and provide information but also construct a gendered version of reality. It is noteworthy how the construction of gender depends on the format of the newspaper itself, particularly the choice of topics and genres fused with the audience's expectations. Thus, among the sixteen pages of the "Mirror of the Week", a quarter of the column is directly allocated to the woman: it is about the Japanese jazz pianist and composer Hiromi Uehara. The rest of the newspaper space is devoted to the activities of men, which according to this distribution, naturally, is perceived as the norm. Men appear in articles on domestic and foreign policy, economics and business, innovations in modern accounting, health care, literature and academic life; twelve "serious" photographs support their essential status in society. At the same time, the Japanese Hiromi Uehara was photographed while expressively playing the piano, and another representative - ballerina Natalia Osipova - is seen in the photo next to her husband, Ivan Vasiliev. The interview of the latter concludes the column on culture. That is, the space for women in this weekly is reserved only within the framework of art. However, even then, it is possible that the article about the pianist will not be a report from the festival without a word from the actress herself, and the famous ballerina was mentioned only in an interview with her husband - and this is what we see in the newspaper.

Considering that the social importance of an event and a person is created precisely through media mediation, which makes certain groups of people influential, and their actions - important, it can be concluded that the analyzed issue supports male hegemony not only at the highest levels of government but also in all spheres of public life. On the other hand, a woman's activities and difficulties (unequal pay,

employment, childbirth, maternity problems, domestic violence, sexual harassment, anorexia) are not mentioned, not problematic, but pushed out of the media reality.

The newspaper *Ukraina Moloda* (2012) shares space for women in articles on world art (note on Lucia McAdam Freud's exhibition), Ukrainian television, interview with Oksana Kucherova, a TV producer on several 1 + 1 projects, photos Tina Karol and Svitlana Loboda on the show "Voice of the Country", sexual slavery, in which Ukrainian women fall abroad, and catwalk activities of models (of course, the last page is full of photos of models wearing sconces). Although the publication positions itself as a "daily information and political newspaper", its entertainment and focus on pop culture (singers, TV shows, diets) are apparent.

Moreover, in the very first column of the interview with director Lubomyr Levitsky, the following quote was announced: "The viewer reacts equally to either the explosion of the Kremlin or a naked girl" (Kulik, 2010, p. 110) — that is, the naked female body predominates not only visually, it is also used as a peppercorn for better perception of texts.

At the same time, the theme of Ukrainian women suffering from sexual slavery and slave labour in the world is developed in the best traditions of action drama. As modern Cossacks save Ukrainian Cossacks: "Obviously, in the case of Igor Gnat, the genetic code laid down in the distant times when the Cossacks went to the shores of the Crimea and Turkey to slave markets worked. However, unlike the Cossacks, who hoped for their sword and faithful horse, modern heroes hope only for their happiness and luck" (Sitchak, 2012, p. 7). The girls themselves "fell into the hands of perverts or pimps" are not given the floor, the motives for their actions, instead, explains their saviour Igor Gnat. The story is a fairy tale: a fearless warrior saves women victims. Not surprisingly, the announcement of the article again hits the front page.

In turn, concludes the issue of the message "Winged and coveted" - about the show of lingerie manufacturer, which is full of remarks "who are thin and who is worse": birth in September of the second child. Although, from the point of view of the average person, a young mother looks brilliant. Reports of the effects of anorexia would not be as spectacular as photos of "figure-hugging" models in bras with precious stones but are more socially valuable than the latter. After all, it is known how many girls chasing the standards of skinny models cripple their health. However, the media in this regard instead support the splendour of the rich world, in which the \$ 2.5 million on the slender body of the model is valued above the health of real women.

In the newspaper "Po-ukrainski" (2012), a woman appears among the five best doctors of the Lviv region, as well as in the columns "Culture" (Lada Luzina was naked for the photo project "Dying Kyiv", 2012, p. 7), "World" (Hulk's Footballer's Sister Kidnapped, 2012, p. 3), "Elections" ("Lesya Orobets took the seal out of the commission chairman's panties", 2012, p. 6), "Scandals" ("Antonina Kolmakova owes the bank 4.5 million hryvnias", 2012, p. 5), "Language" (interview with a teacher of Ukrainian as a foreign language at the Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, 2012, p. 8). In other words, the publication presents women in two ways: on the one hand, as an expert in medicine, law or language teaching, and on the other hand, it produces sexist statements. In particular, the mechanism of subordination of the woman is evidenced by a note about the kidnapped sister Hulk. If her brother were not known, the information about her abduction would hardly have hit the headlines. The victimization of women in several articles, the symbolic annihilation of officials (reports that Lesia Orobets has removed the seal from the commission chairman's panties), and the fact that women are more likely to appear in scandalous reports than in serious ones are noteworthy. All these mechanisms create gender polarization,

reduce the relationship of dependence and subordination between women and men, and symbolically diminish the role and importance of women in society.

At the same time, the analyzed edition shows a slightly different approach to the female body than the previous one. For example, a photo of a naked woman draws attention to the destruction of the old architecture of Kyiv, thanks to which the female body becomes a means of symbolic struggle.

Based on an analysis of the topics in which the three newspapers write about women, we can conclude that they seem to be in parallel realities, although they are published almost daily. One or another construction of gender depends primarily on targeting a specific audience. For instance, *The Mirror of the Week* (2012) writes seriously, but not about women. "Young Ukraine" to attract readers, even acute social issues can be reduced to a fairy tale about the Cossacks and robbers. *Gazeta Po-Ukrainski* writes about women both seriously and in a discriminatory way — the latter, however, happens more often; in particular, women are more likely than men to appear in scandalous reports.

The polarization of women and men in the media space becomes even more apparent when compared to whom the media gives the right to an expert vote. Although it is believed that unbiased coverage of an event or fact can be achieved by presenting different views on the problem, the choice of expert or experts is part of the ideology, as it affects the perception and ways to solve problems.

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Thus, the analysis of newspaper issues showed that the dominant groups (heterosexual men) from many reviews have a better chance to present their descriptions of events as authoritative and neutral, and it is their definitions that the media often present as reality. On the other hand, people from minorities (women, homosexuals) do not have such an expert voice, even on issues that directly concern them (for example, Ukrainian women who suffer from sexual slavery).

In our view, the question of expert position or voice is fundamental to understanding how the media constructs gender polarization: to whom is it delegated the right to express their views on the broader consequences of certain events (what they mean for the country, government, business, etc.) and to whom they address as a victim, victim or eyewitness of accidents, private persons.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, analyzing frame analysis in journalism based on scientists' research can be used to frame feminism in the media. Framing feminism in the media can be used to interpret or manipulate when reporting specific facts. Moreover, popular news resources cover the broadest range of topics and events, so framing feminism in the news gives the most accurate picture of feminist media discourse. Feminist discourse is inherent in publications on various topics: politics, culture, and science. However, the frame of "feminism" is associated with the smallest number of publications; most publications are associated with the frame of "gender".

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